

Review Article

A Review on Social Media Trends and Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

The rapid expansion of social media has introduced a powerful marketing strategy known as social media marketing (SMM), which has become a central focus of research across various disciplines. This study seeks to identify trends and priority areas within the scientific literature on SMM through a bibliometric analysis. Using VOS viewer software, the study examined 1,824 articles published between 2011 and 2022 in the Scopus database. Additionally, a systematic review of 997 papers was conducted to pinpoint the most influential authors, journals, and articles in the field. The analysis revealed key trends such as publication growth, leading journals, prominent institutions, countries, and collaboration networks. The findings highlight a substantial increase in SMM research, with the Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing publishing the highest number of articles. Australia and the United States emerged as the leading contributors, with Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter identified as the most frequently studied platforms. These insights provide valuable guidance for optimizing social media strategies and aligning them with current trends.

Keywords: Bibliometric analysis, social media marketing, VOS viewer, scientific publication, research.

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Introduction

In today's digital age, social networking platforms have become essential to daily life, with over 95% of individuals globally following at least one brand on social media (Ibrahim et al., 2020). As of 2021, more than 4.26 billion people used social media worldwide, with projections estimating this number will reach nearly six billion by 2027 (Statista, 2023). Social media has revolutionized consumer behavior by providing new avenues for searching, evaluating, selecting, and purchasing goods and services (Alves et al., 2016). Consequently, social media has emerged as a unique digital marketing channel, enabling advertisers to engage consumers through interactive and information-sharing advertisements (Appel et al., 2020). Social media is recognized as a highly effective marketing tool that hinges on customer engagement (Kumar & Pansari, 2016). In social media marketing (SMM), the focus extends beyond products to people, allowing users to create advertising content—known as user-generated content—and become unofficial brand ambassadors (Barquero Cabrero et al., 2023). SMM empowers individuals and companies to promote their websites, products, or services through online social channels, reaching a broader audience that traditional advertising may not have accessed (Karimi & Naghibi, 2015).

The growing importance of social media has spurred an increase in research exploring its role in marketing. It is crucial for academic scholars to regularly analyze existing research to gain a comprehensive understanding of the intellectual landscape and anticipate future trends in the field (Csordás et al., 2014). Despite its significance, research on trends among scholars in social media marketing remains limited. Addressing this gap, this paper presents one of the first bibliometric analyses specifically investigating social media marketing trends. It is also the first study to combine bibliometric analysis with a systematic review in this field.

Unlike previous bibliometric studies on social media marketing, this research takes a broader and deeper approach, examining the influence of academic institutions, scholars, journals, and countries. For instance, Barkha and Rathee (2023) conducted a bibliometric analysis of the term "social media marketing" to explore trends, key contributors, and thematic focuses in academic literature, analyzing 980 articles related to marketing management. They identified twelve clusters of research trends within marketing management articles related to social media. In contrast, this study analyzed 1,824 articles over an 11-year period and conducted a systematic review of 997 papers using a multi-stage selection process. This paper not only provides insights into the current state of social media marketing research but also assesses the future direction of the field, offering a valuable resource for scholars planning future research endeavours.

The specific objectives of this article include:

- Identifying prominent and influential scholars in social media marketing research and examining their collaborations.
- Ranking leading countries and institutions in social media marketing research and analyzing their co-authorship patterns.

- Examining the co-occurrence of keywords in social media marketing publications.
- Assessing the utilization and relative prevalence of various social media platforms in the literature.

Background

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted the global market, leading to a marked decrease in visits to physical stores as consumers shifted to online shopping. Social media played a crucial role during this period, providing a platform for the public to express their opinions and for businesses to maintain visibility (Hsu & Hung, 2022). This unique feature of social media has revolutionized marketing, particularly in terms of interaction and promotion, enabling businesses to reach their target audiences at a lower cost compared to traditional advertising methods (Hagan et al., 2021). Marketing, as a well-established discipline, continuously evolves in response to new developments and needs. The role of marketing in business development has undergone a radical transformation with the widespread adoption of internet communication, especially through the rise of social media (Sudirjo et al., 2023). Social media platforms not only open up new possibilities for brand communication but also empower customers, providing a personal channel for user-generated content and social interactions (Ebrahim, 2020). In social media marketing (SMM), common elements include the use of social platforms and the encouragement of users to spread content through interaction, information sharing, and word of mouth (Yadav & Rahman, 2017). SMM involves leveraging social media platforms to create, communicate, deliver, and exchange offerings that add value to a company's stakeholders (Jacobson et al., 2020). More comprehensively, SMM can be defined as the process by which businesses build and maintain relationships with stakeholders, enhancing their value through interaction, information sharing, personalized purchase recommendations, and word-of-mouth promotion (Varela-Neira et al., 2022). The purposes of using SMM include branding, promotion, market research, customer service, and customer relationship management activities (Jaakonmäki et al., 2017). Based on the findings of previous studies, companies can significantly benefit from making SMM an integral element of their overall business strategy; SMM not only has a positive effect on customer retention, but also on purchase intention, moreover it has a positive impact on a company's brand, which can take the form of brand meaning, brand equity, brand loyalty and brand sustainability (Dwivedi et al., 2021). By considering the related literature, we can realize that researchers have become more interested in studying the key elements of SMM in a variety of contexts and perspectives. Pang et al. (2020) carried out a bibliometric analysis on social media marketing the development status and quantitative analysis; by analyzing 477 articles from 2009 to the first half of 2020, the paper revealed the most influential authors, journals and articles within the context of SMM. In another study Ghorbani et al. (2021) applied bibliometric analysis to examine 924 articles regarding trends and patterns in digital marketing published from 1979 to 2020 and stated that SMM is one of the top 20 most repeated emerging keywords in the digital marketing area. Similarly, Dunakhe and Panse (2022) reviewed the impact of digital marketing between 2012 and 2020, highlighting the fading distinction between "Marketing" and "Digital Marketing" as digital elements increasingly permeate all marketing efforts. Purnomo et al. (2021) conducted a bibliometric analysis of digital marketing on an international scale, analyzing

1,023 scientific documents published between 1982 and 2019. Their study identified the most active institutions and scientists in digital marketing research and mapped global collaborative networks.

Krishen et al. (2021) employed computational techniques, such as growth curve analysis and citation network analysis, to trace the evolution of key themes, articles, and research dynamics in interactive digital marketing. Ismagilova et al. (2021) offered a unified perspective on the return on investment (ROI) in SMM through a bibliometric analysis of 115 outputs from the Web of Science database, covering the period from 2009 to 2020. Alves et al. (2016) reviewed 44 academic papers on SMM, noting that most studies focused on either the consumer perspective or how companies can maximize value from social media channels. Alalwan et al. (2017) conducted a concept-driven systematic review of 144 articles, summarizing themes such as the role of social media in advertising, electronic word-of-mouth, customer relationship management, and brand performance.

Misirlis and Vlachopoulou (2018) reviewed 52 articles on social media metrics and analytics in marketing, published between 2010 and 2016. Their study highlighted trends in tourism, Facebook and Twitter as dominant platforms, and consumer-centric marketing as key concepts in SMM strategies. Arora and Sanni (2019) reviewed literature published in the *Journal of Promotion Management* from 2007 to 2017, identifying research themes in SMM based on past, current, and emerging trends. Their analysis showed balanced application of social media variables across studies, despite most research being quantitatively oriented. They identified gaps in recent SMM research, proposed new directions, and offered implications for both theoretical understanding and practical application.

Materials and methods

This study employed a bibliometric analysis and systematic review to identify trends in social media marketing research. The bibliometric approach utilizes quantitative tools to analyze bibliographic data (Broadus, 1987), while systematic literature reviews rely on qualitative techniques (MacCoun, 1998). Bibliometric procedures generally fall into two main categories: 1) performance analysis and 2) science mapping (Cobo et al., 2011). Performance analysis evaluates the contributions of various research constituents, whereas science mapping focuses on the relationships between these constituents (Donthu et al., 2021).

This paper applied both performance analysis and science mapping to identify the most prolific authors, publications, and countries in the field, and to illustrate co-occurrence and co-authorship trends. Keyword co-occurrence analysis is based on the assumption that the presence of two keywords in multiple documents indicates a conceptual relationship between them (Pesta et al., 2018). Authors typically select keywords that best represent the primary focus of their studies. Co-authorship analysis, on the other hand, is the most formal indicator of intellectual collaboration in scientific research. It involves the joint participation of authors, often leading to higher-quality or more substantial research outputs (Acedo et al., 2006). Understanding these collaborative relationships is essential for assessing scholarly interactions. Additionally, the study reviewed the selected articles to evaluate their relevance and methodologies within the context of

marketing. Following the recommendations of Donthu et al. (2021), a three-pronged procedure was applied to conduct the bibliometric analysis effectively.

Figure 1. research procedure

The analysis and visualization of data in this study were performed using the VOS viewer software program, following the methodology outlined by Van Eck and Waltman (2010). Additionally, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify current trends in social media marketing. The following sections will provide a detailed summary of the methods and measures employed in this study.

Data collection

The data for this research were sourced from Scopus, chosen for its comprehensive coverage of peer-reviewed research in our study area, which surpasses that of the Web of Science (Valtakoski, 2020). Building on the work of Krishen et al. (2021) and Leung et al. (2017) on social media, we developed a list of seven social media-related keywords: "Social Media Marketing," "Marketing on Instagram," "Marketing on Facebook," "Marketing on Twitter," "Marketing on LinkedIn," "Marketing on Pinterest," and "Marketing on TikTok." These keywords were used to conduct an initial search of titles, abstracts, and keywords up to March 2023, yielding a total of 2,149 papers.

The initial sample was refined by applying additional exclusion criteria. Filters were applied based on publication type (Article, Conference Paper, Book, Book Chapter), year (2011-2022), and language (English). This process resulted in a final dataset of 1,824 articles. The collected data were analyzed and visualized according to various characteristics: the number of publications, leading journals in the field, contributing institutions, country/territory, h-index, collaboration patterns, and citation metrics.

We further analyzed the data to explore the relationships among countries, authors, and key social media marketing (SMM) keywords, visualizing the primary clusters within each category using VOS viewer software (v.1.6.18). Finally, a systematic review conducted between 2022 and 2023 identified key trends, resulting in a focused analysis of 997 papers.

Data Analysis

The data analysis in this study was conducted in three phases. First, descriptive statistics were provided. Next, using data from Scopus, VOS viewer was utilized to create clusters that illustrate co-authorship networks and keyword co-occurrence patterns. Finally, a systematic review was performed to gain a deeper understanding of trends in social media marketing (SMM).

Regarding document types, articles were the most prevalent, with 1,328 documents, accounting for 72% of the total publications. Conference papers followed, comprising 323 documents, or 17% of the total. The majority of these articles were written in English, representing approximately 84% of the sample. Most were published in journals focused on business, management, and accounting (57%), with computer science being the next most dominant subject area, accounting for 29%.

Figure 2 illustrates the publication productivity in social media marketing. The number of articles published between 2011 and 2016 was relatively low, but there was a significant surge in interest starting in 2017, which continued steadily until 2022. This trend underscores the growing academic focus on SMM in recent years.

Figure 2. Number of articles changes over time.

Journals and publications

Table 1 lists the ten most active journals in social media marketing. The *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing* leads with 56 published papers, making it the most prolific. It is followed by the *Journal of Business Research* with 29 articles, the *International Journal of Data and Network Science* with 26 papers, and both the *Journal of Digital and Social Media Marketing* and *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, each with 25 articles during the surveyed period.

The citation patterns among these top ten journals provides valuable insights. Notably, the CiteScore of these journals reflects their impact and relevance in the field. According to the 2021 CiteScore report, the journals with the highest CiteScores are the *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* (11.4), the *Journal of Business Research* (11.2), and the *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing* (9.1). These scores highlight the influence and significance of these journals in shaping social media marketing research.

Table 1. Ten Most Influential Journals in Social Media Marketing

Rank	Journal	Tc	Tp	Cite Score 2021	The Most Cited Article	Time Cited/ Cited By	Publisher
1	Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing	351	1553	9.1	Engagement: A Review And Research Agenda(Barger Et Al., 2016).	205	Emerald
2	Journal of Business Research	9416	49307	11.2	Do Social Media Marketing Activities Enhance Customer Equity? An Empirical Study of Luxury Fashion Brand (Kim & Ko, 2012).	1042	Elsevier
3	International Journal of Data and Network Science	367	1101	2.7	Social Media and E-Commerce: A Scientometrics Analysis (Javid Et Al., 2019).	30	Growing Science
4	Journal of Digital and Social Media Marketing	159	63	0.5	Digital Marketing: Incompatibilities Between Performance Marketing And Marketing Creativity (Lies, 2021).	5	Henry Stewart Publications
5	Sustainability	60388	268642	5.0	The Effects of Corporate Social Responsibility Practices	89	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing

Rank	Journal	Tc	Tp	Cite Score 2021	The Most Cited Article	Time Cited/ Cited By	Publisher
					And Environmental Factors Through A Moderating Role of Social Media Marketing on Sustainable Performance of Business Firms (Abbas Et Al., 2019).		Institute (MDPI)
6	ACM International Conference Proceeding Series	93368	44944	1.0	Social Network Marketing: A Segmentation Approach To Understanding Purchase Intention (Smith Et Al., 2016).	6	-
7	Frontiers In Psychology	34311	86951	4.0	What Do Adolescents See on Social Media? A Diary Study of Food Marketing Images on Social Media (Qutteina Et Al., 2019).	46	Frontiers Media S.A.
8	International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising	334	139	1.2	Characteristics of Social-Media Marketing Strategy and Customer-Based Brand Equity Outcomes: A Conceptual Model (Pham & Gammoh, 2015).	34	Inderscience Publishers
9	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	2868	19948	11.4	Social Media Marketing: Comparative Effect of Advertisement Sources (Shareef Et Al., 2019).	214	Elsevier
10	Cogent Business and Management	1,396	3389	2.9	Social Media Marketing Gains Importance After Covid-19 (Mason Et Al., 2021).	54	Cogent OA

Note: Tp: Total Publications; Tc: Total Citation

Leading Authors and their co-authorship

Table 2 presents the fifteen leading authors in social media marketing. Both Australia and the United States feature prominently among these authors. Erik Cambria from

Nanyang Technological University in Singapore stands out as the most influential author, with eight published papers and the highest total citations of 23,414. The next four leading authors, each with seven published articles, are from Australia.

In terms of citation counts, other authors surpass these Australian researchers. For instance, Virender Kumar from St. John's University ranks second with 17,804 citations, while Jennifer E. Rowley from the Faculty of Business and Law ranks third with 13,165 citations. This citation data highlights the varying impact and recognition of these researchers in the field of social media marketing.

Table 2. Leading authors in social media marketing

Rank	Author	Scopus Author ID	TP	H-Index	TC	Current affiliation	Country
1	Cambria, Erik	56140547500	362	80	23414	Nanyang Technological University	Singapore
2	Cheung, Man Lai	57210828583	28	14	574	The University of Newcastle, Australia	Australia
3	Harrigan, Paul	24068435900	60	23	1948	The UWA Business School,	Australia
4	Kumar, Ashish	55661784400	23	9	1056	RMIT University	Australia
5	Rosenberger III, Philip J.	14631113500	30	16	828	Newcastle Business School	Australia
6	Gretzel, Ulrike	6506950250	157	44	8714	University of Southern California	The United States
7	Kumar, Virender	7404634666	222	68	17804	St. John's University	The United States
8	Mathur, Manisha	36727744800	9	5	75	Augusta University	The United States
9	Rowley, Jennifer E.	7201756587	324	57	13165	Manchester Metropolitan University	The United Kingdom
10	Salo, Jari	51562579100	82	24	2426	University of Helsinki	Finland
11	Vrontis, Demetris	57195339008	336	43	6288	University of Nicosia	Cyprus
12	Ahuja, Vandana	36458115200	53	11	308	Amity University	India
13	Antoniadis, Ioannis	57194003875	20	6	125	Western Macedonia University of Applied Sciences	Greece
14	Bezawada, Ram	26639144500	19	9	1132	City University of New York	The United States
15	Hanaysha, Jalal Rajeh	56300136600	42	10	276	Skyline University College	The United Arab Emirates

Note: TP: Total Publications; TC: Total Citation

The author collaboration network highlights the extent of co-authored papers within a specific research domain (Alnajem et al., 2021). Figure 3 illustrates the collaboration network in social media marketing (SMM). The analysis set a threshold of at least three documents and zero citations for author inclusion. Out of 4,210 authors, 182 met these criteria.

The network identified 10 clusters, with 69 links and a total link strength of 93. This network suggests a need for increased collaborative research efforts in SMM. Notably, the most influential authors include Cheung M.L., with seven documents and a total link strength of 15; Rosenberger P.J., with five documents and a total link strength of 13; and Salo J., with six documents and a total link strength of 12.

Figure 3. Author collaboration network in SMM Research

Leading Countries, institutions, and their co-authorship

Table 3 and Figure 4 provide insights into the leading countries in social media marketing (SMM) research and their collaboration patterns. Compared to the author collaboration network, the country collaboration network is denser. Out of 110 countries, 64 met the criteria of having at least three documents.

The United States stands out as the most dominant country with 437 publications and a total link strength of 168, showing substantial collaboration with countries such as the United Kingdom, Australia, China, and South Korea. India, the second most productive country with 230 publications, ranks fifth in the co-authorship network with a total link

strength of 54. The United Kingdom ranks third in terms of publication volume with 137 articles and holds the second position in the co-authorship network with a total link strength of 111.

These findings indicate that global collaborative networks in SMM are not constrained by geographical or linguistic boundaries, though some regional collaborations are evident. Notably, recent contributions to SMM research are increasingly coming from Asian countries, while research activities between 2017 and 2019 were predominantly centered in Europe and the United States.

Table 3. The most influential countries in SMM publications

Rank	Country	Number of documents	h-index	TC	Most Productive Academic Institution
1	The United States	437	58	14045	Florida State University
2	India	230	22	3209	Amity University
3	The United Kingdom	137	32	5394	Manchester Metropolitan University
4	China	127	23	2318	Harbin Institute of Technology
5	Indonesia	105	11	446	Bina Nusantara University
6	Australia	77	23	2012	The University of Newcastle, Australia
7	Malaysia	76	16	690	Universiti Malaya
8	Italy	55	21	2772	Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca
9	Spain	52	16	732	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
10	Taiwan	51	15	1158	Chaoyang University of Technology
11	Turkey	50	10	537	Boğaziçi Üniversitesi
12	South Korea	40	14	1915	Sejong University
13	Germany	38	11	1401	University of Michigan-Dearborn
14	Canada	35	14	1710	Toronto Metropolitan University
15	Greece	34	9	235	Panepistimion Makedonias

Figure 4. National collaboration networks in SMM research

Co-occurrence of Keywords in SMM Publications

Keyword analysis is a valuable tool for identifying key research content, themes, and trends in a field (Chen et al., 2008). This study conducted a co-occurrence analysis of authors' keywords to uncover prevalent themes in social media marketing (SMM). By applying a threshold of three occurrences, the analysis identified 3,822 keywords across SMM articles. The keywords were categorized into several contexts: platforms, such as social media sites like Facebook; business sectors, including industries like tourism, food, fashion, and SMEs; managerial applications, such as social CRM and methods like PLS-SEM; and recent trends, notably those from 2020-2021, including influencers, the elaboration likelihood model, and market orientation. Table 4 details the most frequently used keywords in SMM research, while Figure 5 visualizes these keywords, with node size representing keyword frequency and link width indicating the strength of keyword co-occurrence (Neff & Corley, 2009).

Table 6. The most frequent keywords used by authors

Keyword	Frequency	Keyword	Frequency
Social Media Marketing	722	Instagram	63
Social Media	474	Twitter	53
Facebook	125	Brand Equity	51
Marketing	110	Brand Loyalty	49
Digital Marketing	83	Customer Engagement	37
Purchase Intention	65	Influencer Marketing	36

Table 7. The distribution of reviewed papers among themes with the key platforms and number of used

Theme	No. of Papers	Methodology	Country of Research
Marketing on Instagram	84	quantitative and qualitative	Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, Croatia, Greece, India, Indonesia, Iran, Italy, South Korea, Malaysia, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkey, United Arab Emirates, The United Kingdom, The United States, Venezuela
Marketing on Facebook	94	quantitative and qualitative	Albania, Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, Colombia, Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Egyptian, European, Fiji, Germany, Greece, Hungary, India, Indonesia, Iran, Jordan, Malaysia, Montenegro, New Zealand, Pakistan, Poland, Portugal, Qatar, Romania, South Africa, South Korea, Spain, Taiwan, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, The United Kingdom, The United States, Viet Nam
Marketing on Tik Tok	10	quantitative and qualitative	China, Romania, The United States
marketing on Pinterest	1	qualitative	The United States
Marketing on LinkedIn	8	quantitative and qualitative	The United States, South Africa, Poland, Germany, Malaysia, Norway
Marketing on twitter	42	quantitative and qualitative	Australia, Brazil, Canada, Egypt, Germany, Greece, India, Italy, Malaysia, New Zealand, South Korea, Spain, Switzerland, The United Arab Emirates, The United Kingdom, The United States

A total of 4,210 studies were reviewed, including both quantitative and qualitative research on platforms such as Twitter, TikTok, and LinkedIn. Notably, only one qualitative study focused on Pinterest was conducted in the United States. The analysis revealed that, in 2022, Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter were the most frequently studied and favored platforms among researchers.

Conclusion and discussion

Social media marketing (SMM) is rapidly transforming the landscape of business advertising, offering both opportunities and challenges for companies seeking a competitive advantage. Previous research underscores the significance of social media in marketing, highlighting the need for businesses to leverage new digital platforms to enhance their marketing strategies (Chen, 2023; Gu & Duan, 2024; Laradi et al., 2023) Understanding the role of social media as a marketing tool is therefore crucial.

To explore the latest trends in SMM literature, this study conducted a bibliometric analysis of SMM-related publications using VOSviewer software and data from the Scopus database. A total of 1,824 journal articles were selected and reviewed. The analysis revealed that SMM has emerged as a prominent research area over the past decade, with a significant increase in publications from 2011 to 2022. The Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing was identified as the leading journal in the field, followed by the Journal of Business Research and the International Journal of Data and Network Science. The most productive researchers were Camberia E., Vrontis D., and Rowley JE. while Nanyang Technological University was recognized as the top contributing institution. The research landscape showed a strong presence of publications from developed Western countries such as the US and the UK, which are home to well-established universities. Additionally, significant contributions came from Asian countries, including Singapore and India.

Limitations and further researches

No research is without limitations, and this study is no exception. One key limitation is the reliance on quantitative measures such as publication counts, citations, and co-authorships. While these metrics provide valuable insights into productivity and impact, they do not assess the quality or rigor of the research. Influential articles may receive fewer citations, and bibliometric indicators alone cannot fully capture the research's quality.

Additionally, this study focused exclusively on academic journal articles published in English, excluding potentially significant research published in other languages. This limitation means that some potentially groundbreaking studies may not have been considered. As English is often the primary language for many researchers, the study's scope may disproportionately represent research from English-speaking countries. Future research should incorporate domestic research databases and other languages to obtain a more comprehensive view.

The study also relied on a single database, Scopus, which could limit the breadth of the analysis. Future bibliometric studies would benefit from including additional reputable databases, such as Web of Science, to broaden the scope and enhance the robustness of the findings. Moreover, incorporating other sources of knowledge, such as conference papers, books, and book chapters, could provide a more holistic understanding of the field.

Another consideration is that bibliometric analyses sometimes include self-citations, which can artificially inflate citation counts and affect the perceived impact of certain authors or publications. While self-citations can be legitimate, they may introduce bias and distort the true impact and influence of the research (Nusair et al., 2019). Despite these limitations, this study offers a comprehensive overview of the field and serves as a valuable foundation for further research.

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